

Can reducing technical inefficiencies of pesticides achieve environmental impact targets? The case of Dutch arable farms

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Abstract

Farmers manage each type of pesticide differently, given the varying risks they address. As both damage-abating and polluting inputs, we have incorporated their negative impacts into a non-parametric framework to estimate the technical inefficiency of different pesticides and environmental inefficiency of Dutch arable farms from 2011 to 2021. Results suggest that farmers are more efficient in using insecticides rather than fungicides, herbicides and other pesticides, and have a higher potential to reduce negative pesticide impacts on aquatic organisms compared to soil organisms. However, even with full efficiency, the vast majority of farmers would not meet acceptable pesticide impact levels that are seen as sustainable in the long run.

Keywords: pesticides; technical inefficiencies; environmental impacts; by-production model; arable crop farms..

JEL classification: C23, C67, D22

1. Introduction

Pesticides are essential inputs for protecting crops and livestock from harmful pests and for preserving the shelf life of agricultural products. They serve as important tools for farmers to manage risks while also reducing the labour and fuel that would otherwise be required for manual weed and pest control (Skevas *et al.*, 2012; Carvalho, 2017; Möhring *et al.*, 2020a). However, pesticide use can also have harmful effects on soil, freshwater and marine ecosystems, as well as negative impacts on human health and well-being (Beketov *et al.*, 2013; Sarwar, 2015; Kim *et al.*, 2017). Reducing the adverse impact of pesticides remains a key focus of EU agricultural policy discussions (Möhring *et al.*, 2020c). The recent rejection and withdrawal of the

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proposed Sustainable Use Regulation (SUR) highlights the ongoing challenges in implementing effective policies to reduce pesticide use and mitigate environmental harm (Finger *et al.*, 2024a). At the same time, many farmers remain reluctant to switch to pesticide alternatives and other low-pesticide practices, even when these are considered more sustainable (Wang *et al.*, 2023).

A major reason for this reluctance is the fear of yield losses following a significant reduction in pesticide use. In the EU, Beckman *et al.* (2020) report that full implementation of the EU's Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategies - which include two key non-binding pesticide targets for 2030: a 50 per cent reduction in the use and risk of chemical pesticides and a 50 per cent reduction in the use of more hazardous pesticides - could lead to an average 12 per cent decline in food production. For many farmers, the lack of viable alternatives to chemical pesticides, combined with limited information about the cost-effectiveness of options such as integrated pest management (IPM), makes it challenging to assess their impact on profitability (European Commission, 2023). These uncertainties and economic concerns contribute to widespread pesticide overuse, as farmers seek to manage pests, avoid potential yield losses and meet consumer demand for undamaged products (Skevas *et al.*, 2014; Hüesker and Lepenies, 2022; Tran *et al.*, 2023).

The primary aim of this study is to assess whether there are potential gains to be made by reducing technical and environmental inefficiencies in the use of pesticides. Subsequently, this study also seeks to identify farm-specific contextual drivers of inefficiencies in pesticide use and environmental management. Analysing the degree of inefficiency associated with pesticide use and underscoring the economic incentives for farmers to rectify such inefficiencies could prove to be an important economic incentive. This could particularly be true for farmers with less intrinsic motivation for reducing pesticide usage. In addition to pesticide cuts, the SUR also aimed at promoting the adoption of IPM. However, it is important that the EU simultaneously rebalances the focus of its agricultural policies to include improving pesticide use efficiency, especially in the context of food security uncertainties and competitiveness.

Previous research has devoted significant attention to measuring the technical inefficiency of pesticide use. For Dutch agriculture, several studies - including Oude Lansink and Silva (2004), Skevas *et al.* (2014), Skevas and Oude Lansink (2014), and more recently, Ahovi *et al.* (2021) and Schneider *et al.* (2021) - have reported technical inefficiencies ranging from as low as 2.9 per cent to as high as 37 per cent. These studies, which typically measure pesticide use based on purchase data, often recommend equal reduction in all pesticides. However, the ease with which farmers can reduce specific pesticides may vary considerably. Factors such as the type of pesticide, frequency of application and method of use often differ depending on farm type and the crops cultivated. Economic considerations also play a role: pesticide prices can vary widely, with some products being significantly more expensive, which

may encourage farmers to use them more judiciously. These variations suggest that a uniform reduction approach may not be practical or effective in all farming contexts. More importantly, the target specificity of pesticides differs resulting in unique requirements and constraints depending on the pest pressures and ecological interactions in the field. It is important to note that a pesticide product may contain different active ingredients, each tailored to specific pest management needs. As a result, the choice of a pesticide with different active ingredients enables farmers to manage their effectiveness, pest resistance, environmental and health impact and compliance. Therefore, it is important to recognize the distinct characteristics and negative impacts imposed by fungicides, insecticides, herbicides and other pesticides when evaluating inefficiencies. These drivers of pesticide usage suggest that farmers may allocate different management decisions to the different pesticide types, leading to potential differences in pesticide-specific inefficiencies across farms. This approach offers more detailed insights, enabling precision in recommendations to support sustainable pesticide management strategies.

Another line of research integrates the environmental risks and impacts of pesticide use into farm performance evaluation frameworks (Skevas *et al.*, 2012, 2014; Skevas and Oude Lansink, 2014; Skevas and Serra, 2016). This approach is valuable because it captures the dual role of pesticides in both supporting food production and contributing to environmental degradation. Skevas and Serra (2016), in applying the by-production approach as proposed by Murty *et al.* (2012) provide a valuable framework for understanding pesticide environmental inefficiency under pest pressure. While these studies address important inefficiencies related to the use of pesticides, they fail to assess whether improving pesticide environmental efficiencies align with long-term environmental sustainability goals such as meeting environmental impact targets set by the Dutch Board for the Authorization of Plant Protection Products.

This study contributes to the literature in two key ways. First, it evaluates the technical inefficiencies associated with separate pesticide categories, as well as environmental inefficiencies related to the impacts of pesticides on soil and water organisms. Second, it demonstrates the extent to which improvements in environmental efficiency can help farmers meet regulatory thresholds for pesticide impacts, as defined by relevant environmental standards. The findings of this study have important implications for regulatory bodies and policymakers. By analysing the potential for efficiency improvements to help farms meet regulatory thresholds for pesticide impacts, the study provides valuable insights into the feasibility of achieving current environmental standards under existing farming practices.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Sections 2 and 3 describe the methodology and the data, respectively. Section 4 presents the results, followed by the discussion in Section 5. Section 6 concludes the paper and outlines key policy implications.

2. Methodology

2.1 Economic, environmental and input inefficiencies

This study treats pesticides as inputs associated with pollution and, to account for this, models farm production technology using the by-production approach (Førsund, 2008; Dakpo, 2016; Dakpo and Oude Lansink, 2019). The by-production model assumes that the overall production technology, denoted as $\psi(t)$, is the intersection of sub-technologies; in this case, two sub-technologies, one for the production of conventional good outputs $\psi_g(t)$ and the other for the generation of bad outputs $\psi_b(t)$. Inputs are distinguished into sub-vectors. We let $\nu(t)$ represent the vector of variable inputs ($\nu \in \mathbb{R}_+^J$), $p(t)$ a vector of pesticides ($p \in \mathbb{R}_+^J$), $f(t)$ a vector of fixed inputs ($f \in \mathbb{R}_+^S$). For the outputs, $y(t)$ represents a vector of good outputs ($y \in \mathbb{R}_+^Q$) and $b(t)$ the vector of bad outputs ($b \in \mathbb{R}_+^B$). We assume that pesticides are crop protection inputs that are used exclusively to protect plant health. We further distinguish inputs into polluting (material) and non-polluting (immaterial) inputs following the work of Murty *et al.* (2012). Fixed inputs ($f \in \mathbb{R}_+^S$) are assumed to be non-polluting (immaterial) inputs. This is based on practical reasons since fixed inputs are not involved in the chemical reactions or processes that generate pollution. The intersecting technologies are represented as

$$\psi(t) = \psi_g(t) \cap \psi_b(t), \tag{1}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_g(t) = \{(\nu(t), p(t), y(t)) : (\nu(t), p(t),) \\ \text{can produce } y(t) \text{ given } f(t)\}, \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_b(t) = \{(\nu(t), p(t), y(t)) : (\nu(t), p(t),) \\ \text{can generate } b(t) \text{ given } f(t)\}. \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

The good output sub-technology is characterized by the following properties: (1) no-free-lunch condition and inactivity, (2) input essentiality and attainability, (3) non-emptiness and closedness, (4) boundedness, (5) positive monotonicity in production inputs, (6) free disposability of good output, (7) reverse nestedness and (8) convexity in production inputs. Under the assumption of variable returns to scale (VRS), meaning that increases in inputs do not necessarily result in proportional increases in outputs - the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) formulation for the good output technology, $\psi_g(t)$ is defined as

follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \psi_g(t) &= (v(t), p(t), f(t), y(t), b(t)) : \\
 y_o(t) &\leq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n y_n^g(t), \\
 v_o(t) &\geq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n v_n^g(t) \\
 p_o(t) &\geq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n p_n^g(t), \\
 f_o(t) &\geq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n f_n^g(t), \quad \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n = 1 \\
 \lambda_n &\geq 0, \quad n = 1, \dots, N \\
 (v(t), p(t), k(t), f(t), y(t), b(t)) &\in \mathbb{R}_+^{J+J+S+Q+B}, \quad (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

where λ_n refers to the intensity (weight) of farm n in the good output sub-technology, whereas $y_o(t)$ refers to good output of the evaluated farm n .

The bad output sub-technology is characterized by the following properties: (1) boundedness, (2) essentiality of polluting inputs, (3) convexity in polluting inputs and the bad output, (4) positive monotonicity in the bad output and (5) negative monotonicity in polluting inputs. Further details on these properties can be found in [Dakpo and Ang \(2019\)](#). Assuming VRS, the environmentally bad output sub-technology is defined using DEA as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \psi_b(t) z &= (v(t), p(t), k(t), f(t), y(t), b(t)) : \\
 b_o(t) &\geq \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n y_n^b(t), \quad v_o(t) \leq \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n v_n^b(t) \\
 p_o(t) &\leq \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n p_n^b(t) \\
 f_o(t) &\geq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n f_n^b(t), \\
 \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n &= 1, \quad \varphi_n \geq 0, \\
 n &= 1, \dots, N \\
 (v(t), p(t), f(t), y(t), b(t)) &\in \mathbb{R}_+^{J+J+L+S+Q+B}. \quad (5)
 \end{aligned}$$

To properly represent the by-production model, the bad output sub-technology is assigned a separate intensity variable φ . This differentiation captures the distinct resource requirements and characteristics of the two sub-technologies and their respective impacts on good and bad outputs. φ_n refers to the weight of the farm n in the bad output sub-technology. $b_o(t)$ refers to the bad outputs.

In combining the properties of the two sub-technologies, the overall production technology is formulated as $\psi(t) = \{(v(t), p(t), i(t), f(t), y(t), b(t))\}$:

$$y_o(t) \leq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n y_n^g(t),$$

$$v_o(t) \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n v_n^g(t)$$

$$p_o(t) \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n p_n^g(t),$$

$$f_o(t) \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n f_n^g(t)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n = 1$$

$$b_o(t) \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n y_n^b(t)$$

$$v_o(t) \leq \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n v_n^b(t),$$

$$p_o(t) \leq \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n p_n^b(t)$$

$$f_o(t) \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n f_n^b(t)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n = 1$$

$$(v(t), p(t), f(t), y(t), b(t)) \in \mathbb{R}_+^{J+J+S+Q+B}. \tag{6}$$

There are two ways by which our approach extends the work of [Murty et al. \(2012\)](#). First, we follow [Dakpo \(2016\)](#) in adding the dependence constraints (7) to the model. These additional constraints link the two sub-technologies and ensure that the optimal levels of polluting inputs are consistent across both technologies. Moreover, these constraints allow our model formulation to comply with the material balance principle.¹ Without these constraints, the implication is that a decision-making unit can become efficient by being projected on two frontiers using different levels of inputs. Earlier applications of this extension include ([Dakpo and Oude Lansink, 2019](#); [Skevas et al., 2023](#); [Bernini and Galli, 2024](#))

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n v_n^b(t) &= \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n v_n^g(t), \quad \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n p_n^b(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n p_n^g(t) \\ \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n f_n^b(t) &= \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n f_n^g(t). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Secondly, we incorporate positive monotonicity in fixed inputs within the bad output technology (see [Appendices II and III](#)). Although these inputs are largely non-polluting and typically associated with the good output technology, we argue - consistent with [Førsund \(2018\)](#) - that immaterial inputs can enhance the efficiency of polluting inputs. Consequently, they can directly influence pollution generation by improving process control, reducing waste and enabling more effective recycling ([Chambers et al., 2014](#)).

To address the curse of dimensionality and reduce the model's computational complexity, revenue (good output) is not expanded. This is based on the evidence that Dutch arable farmers have, on average, typically maximized the potential to increase good outputs. For this reason, we take an input-oriented approach in calculating a directional distance function allowing for simultaneous reduction in bad outputs and inputs. The estimated reductions in bad outputs and inputs correspond to environmental and technical inefficiency scores, respectively. Directional vectors g_b , g_p and g_v are chosen to, respectively, represent the observed values of bad output, pesticides and variable inputs. For pesticides, directional vectors are further individualized for each pesticide category: fungicides (g_{fu}), herbicides (g_{he}), insecticides (g_{in}) and other pesticides (g_{os}). These vectors allow for percentage interpretation of the inefficiency scores of the evaluated farm.

The DEA formulation is $\max_{\beta, \varphi, \lambda} \frac{1}{L_g} (\beta_b + \beta_v + \beta_{fu} + \beta_{he} + \beta_{in} + \beta_{os})$ subject to constraints in [Appendix 3](#).

¹ [Ayres and Kneese \(1969\)](#) proposed the material balance principle, which is based on the idea that the production of pollution is inherent and in general part of the production and consumption process. Therefore, it is impossible to generate pollutants without the use of polluting-generating inputs. For this study, the implication is that a proportional increase or decrease in pesticides induces a similar increase or decrease in the associated environmental impact.

β_b , β_p and β_v refer to the inefficiency related to bad outputs, pesticides and variable inputs, respectively. β_b indicate the extent to which a farm is environmentally inefficient within the context of pesticide use. \mathcal{L}_g refers to the number of decision variables in the objective function which is applied to estimate the average inefficiency of all variables.

2.2 Explaining environmental and pesticide inefficiency

While the DEA model quantifies inefficiencies in pesticide use and their environmental impacts, it does not identify the underlying causes. To address this, we conduct a second-stage regression to explore factors driving or enabling inefficiencies. Moreover, DEA-estimated scores are serially correlated, so caution is needed when selecting a regression technique to explain inefficiency scores. To address this, [Simar and Wilson \(2007\)](#) developed single and double truncated bootstrap methods that allow for valid statistical inference. In this study, we employ the single truncated bootstrap regression and define the regression model as follows:

$$\beta_{b_n} = \alpha + \eta T + \delta Z_n + \varepsilon_n, \quad (8)$$

where β_{b_n} is the environmental inefficiency associated with the bad output of farm n . T depicts temporal fixed effects to capture changes in weather, severe incidence of pests and diseases and technological changes with the vector of response parameters η . Z is the unique set of farm-specific characteristics that serve as explanatory variables in our analysis. The vector δ refers to coefficients associated with these variables, while ε denotes the error term within our model. ε is assumed truncated normal with mean zero, unknown variance and left truncated at point $0 - \delta Z$. The maximum likelihood method is used to obtain estimates $\hat{\delta}$ of δ and standard deviation of the error term $\hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon$ from the truncated regression of β_{b_n} on Z using only inefficient observations. Next, $\hat{\delta}$ and Z are used to generate linear predictions of inefficiency score ($\hat{\beta}_{b_n}$) based on the estimated coefficients and the producer-specific characteristics.

For 2,000 iterations, errors are sampled out of the truncated normal distribution using the computed variance $\hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon$. Subsequently, truncated regression models are computed for all iterations by regressing the farm-specific characteristics on the predicted inefficiency scores. Lastly, confidence intervals of the estimated coefficients are computed based on the empirical distribution to conclude on the statistical significance. Parameter estimates are only indicative of the direction of the relationship between inefficiency and farm characteristics. To provide economic interpretation to these directional associations, marginal effects are computed at the mean of the explanatory variables. Marginal effects measure the effect a unit increase/decrease in a particular explanatory variable has on the predicted inefficiency score. The marginal effects of a variable that

is left-truncated at 0 are defined as follows:

$$\frac{\partial E(\widehat{\beta}_{b_n} | Z_n, \widehat{\beta}_{b_n} > 0)}{\partial Z_n} = \left[1 - \frac{Z_n' \hat{\delta}^*}{\hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^*} * \frac{\phi\left(\frac{Z_n' \hat{\delta}^*}{\hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^*}\right)}{\Phi\left(\frac{Z_n' \hat{\delta}^*}{\hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^*}\right)} - \right] \left[\frac{\phi\left(\frac{Z_n' \hat{\delta}^*}{\hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^*}\right)}{\Phi\left(\frac{Z_n' \hat{\delta}^*}{\hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^*}\right)} \right]^2 \hat{\delta}^*, \quad (9)$$

where β_{b_n} is the inefficiency score, Z_n is an explanatory variable, $\hat{\delta}^*$ is estimated coefficient of the explanatory variables obtained from the bootstrap-truncated regression, $\hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^*$ is the standard deviation of the error term, $\phi(\cdot)$ is the standard normal distribution and $\Phi(\cdot)$ the standard normal cumulative distribution function.

3. Data

The empirical analysis uses data from Dutch arable farms over the period 2011–21, provided by Wageningen Economic Research (WECR). WECR collects farm-level data for the EU Farm Accounting Data Network (FADN) using stratified sampling. The dataset includes revenue and expenses, as well as farm and farmer characteristics. Because DEA scores are particularly sensitive to outliers, we follow WECR in defining arable farms as those where at least 66 per cent of total annual farm revenue is derived from the sale of arable crops (Roskam *et al.* 2022). The final dataset used for estimation consists of 1,561 observations from 240 individual farms. The panel is unbalanced, with farms remaining in the sample for an average of approximately 7 years.

3.1 Variables in the DEA model

The by-production model (8) distinguishes one good output, two bad outputs, two groups of variable inputs and a set of fixed inputs. The good output is represented by total revenue (in euros) generated from the sale of all products, excluding subsidies. The first group of variable inputs includes expenditures on inputs such as energy, fertilizers, seeds, other material and relevant crop-specific costs. The second group of variable inputs consists of four categories of pesticides - fungicides, herbicides, insecticide and others - measured in kilograms of active ingredients applied.

For the farms in our sample, potatoes constitute a significant share of the crop portfolio. This likely explains the high usage of fungicides, as farmers apply them to prevent or minimize the impact of late blight and other fungal diseases affecting potatoes. The relatively low use of insecticides can be attributed to the generally lower insect pest pressure in the Netherlands, especially when compared to the more persistent risks posed by fungal diseases and weeds on arable farms. It is important to note that the pesticide category data may include various active ingredients. These categories are based on individual pesticides, which have been converted into kilograms of active ingredients according to their product concentrations and application rates, and subsequently grouped into the relevant pesticide categories by the WECR. Fixed

inputs include land, labour and capital, expressed in total hectares, hours and euros, respectively. Capital is represented by the stock of machinery, buildings and installations. Both revenue and expenses, including balance sheet values for capital assets, are deflated to real values using the Törnqvist index, with 2015 as the base year. Implicit quantities of inputs and outputs are derived by dividing their monetary values by the corresponding price indices obtained from Eurostat.

Bad outputs are represented by pesticide environmental spillover indicators, reflecting impacts on soil organisms and on ground and surface water organisms. These environmental indicators are expressed as Environmental Impact Points (EIPs) and are calculated by the Dutch Centre for Agriculture and Environment (CLM). EIPs quantify the negative environmental pressures associated with the presence of all pesticides in soil and water ecosystems (<https://www.milieumeetlat.nl/nl/hoewerkt-het-open-teelt.html>). The more EIPs a pesticide receives, the greater its environmental impact. For pesticide impacts on soil organisms, the EIP calculation is based on the chemical properties of the active ingredients - specifically their persistence, mobility in soil and toxicity. It also takes into account the organic matter (OM) content of the soil. For the farms in this study, the CLM applies OM values ranging from 3 to 6 per cent. The OM content, combined with the chemical properties of the pesticide, jointly determines the extent to which pesticides persist in the soil over time. The timing and method of application influence both the rate of degradation and the transport of pesticides within the soil, as well as the amount emitted to surface water. When calculating impact points for water organisms, the assessment takes into account pesticide toxicity and the estimated spray drift to watercourses - assumed to be 1 per cent for arable farming (Reus and Leendertse, 2000). For each farm in the sample, the impact points under a standard application rate (1 kg/ha) are multiplied by the actual quantity applied per hectare by the farmer each year. Overall, the farm-specific impact on soil and water organisms is then calculated by summing the impact points from individual pesticide applications. Since 1995, the Board for the Authorization of Plant Protection Products and Biocides (CTGB) has set acceptable levels (ALs) of 100 and 10 impact points per hectare for soil and water organisms, respectively, with the latter being much stricter to protect water quality. However, in 2013, the CTGB raised the AL for water organisms by a factor of 10, thereby aligning it with the soil threshold. This adjustment was based on new scientific evidence indicating that a higher safety factor - 100 instead of 10 - was more appropriate.

3.2 Variables in the bootstrap truncated regression model

In general, technical efficiency is closely linked to farm management decisions (Zhengfei and Oude Lansink, 2006). As a result, it is standard practice to examine the relationship between estimated technical inefficiency scores and farm characteristics (Skevas *et al.*, 2012; Skevas and Oude Lansink, 2020; Schneider *et al.*, 2021; Adamie and Hansson, 2022). This section outlines

the conceptual framework used to select and incorporate farm- and farmer-specific variables in the bootstrap truncated regression model presented in Section 2.2.

Age is measured in years and refers to the age of the farm manager. The effect of age on efficiency yields mixed conclusions in the literature. Some studies find that older farmers are positively associated with productivity growth, attributing this to improved managerial decisions that come with experience (Zhengfei and Oude Lansink, 2006). Younger farmers, on the other hand, may possess higher levels of education and be more inclined to adopt advanced technologies, which can enhance pest management strategies, potentially improving pesticide use efficiency and reducing environmental impacts (Bozoğlu and Ceyhan, 2007; Mohd Suhaimi et al., 2017).

Subsidy refers to all payments received by the farmer under the Common Agricultural Policy from the EU, as well as additional monetary support from the national government, expressed in euros. CAP payments include basic income support, single farm payments and payment rights. The additional national payments aim to incentivize the transition of the Dutch agricultural sector towards more sustainable practices, covering schemes such as nature conservation, organic farming transitions and extensification, among others. To avoid capturing farm-size effects, subsidies are expressed as payments per hectare (Minviel and Latruffe, 2017). Subsidies may not be considered a direct input, but when effectively invested, they can enhance the productivity of other production inputs (Kumbhakar and Lien, 2010). Conversely, if perceived as supplementary income, subsidies may reduce farmers' motivation to limit pesticide use (Zhu and Oude Lansink, 2010; Zhu et al., 2012).

Farmers who take out *crop insurance* may exhibit reduced pesticide and environmental inefficiency, as they are more likely to rely on insurance contracts rather than excessive pesticide use as a risk management strategy. Additionally, higher insurance coverage may encourage farmers to pursue riskier but potentially more productive investments, which could in turn reduce inefficiency through increased output (Farrin and Miranda, 2015; Zubor-Nemes, 2021). The insurance variable was transformed into a binary indicator (dummy variable) for each year in the dataset. A value of 1 is assigned if the farmer participated in insurance that year, and 0 if not. This approach ensures accurate recording of insurance participation on a year-by-year basis, reflecting whether or not a farmer was insured during each specific year. Consequently, the variable captures year-specific insurance participation.

Farmers may also diversify crop production to reduce pest infestation or as an alternative to taking out insurance. The Herfindahl–Hirschman index (HHI) is used as a proxy for farm *specialization* (Dimara et al., 2005; Kim et al., 2012). It is calculated by summing the squared revenue shares from all individual farm activities and other sources of income. An HHI value approaching 1 indicates a high degree of specialization, while a value closer to 0 denotes a more diversified arable crop production. As shown in Table 1, the average HHI of 0.76 suggests that farms are, on average, specialized. While

Table 1. Summary statistics.

Variable	Dimension	Mean	Standard deviation
Revenue	1,000 euros	583	611
Land	Ha	133	128
Labour	Hours	4,725	3,957
Capital	1,000 euros	817	1076
Variable inputs	1,000 euros	311	294
Fungicides	Kg	560	843
Herbicides	Kg	366	385
Insecticides	Kg	11	25
Other pesticides	Kg	513	814
Pesticide impact on soil organisms	1,000 EIP	52.8	100
Pesticide impact on water organisms	1,000 EIP	231.9	292
<i>Socio-economics</i>			
Age	10 years	5.50	0.99
Subsidy per hectare	100 euros	4.08	1.84
Specialization	Ratio [0,1]	0.76	0.148
Debt ratio	Per cent	76.60	17.27
Insurance	Dummy	0.10	0.29
Clay soil	Per cent	71	44.34
Sandy soil	Per cent	25	41.58
Loess	Per cent	2	13.83
Farms with potatoes	Per cent	92	–

specialist farms may enhance pesticide efficiency through focused management efforts (Guesmi and Serra, 2015), more diversified farms could benefit from the pest control synergies provided by biodiversity, leading to reduced reliance on pesticides and improved environmental efficiency (Skevas *et al.*, 2018).

A farm's *debt ratio* reflects the proportion of its assets financed through debt. When debt is invested in modern technologies or precision agriculture, it can improve both pesticide and environmental efficiencies by enabling better investment opportunities and fostering entrepreneurial approaches (Zhengfei and Oude Lansink, 2006).

Data on soil types are represented by the proportion of farmland covered by peat, loess, clay and sandy soils. Each farm is characterized by the percentage share of these soil types, with the entries summing to 100 per cent. Consequently, only the proportions of loess, clay and sandy soils are included in the regression model, with peat serving as the reference soil type. These soil types are also indicative of regional production patterns in the Netherlands. Clay soils dominate in the western and northern parts of the country, loess in the southern regions and sandy soils in the central and eastern areas (Claessens *et al.*, 2024).

Finally, since the majority of farms include potatoes in their crop production, we control for whether a farm cultivates potatoes by including a binary

Table 2. Environmental and input inefficiencies.^a

Variables	Second quartile	Mean	Third quartile	Per cent of fully efficient observations (whole period)
Environmental				
<i>Pesticide impact on soil organisms</i>	0.000	0.114	0.221	50
<i>Pesticide impact on water organisms</i>	0.216	0.317	0.646	42
Input				
<i>Fungicides</i>	0.109	0.310	0.643	45
<i>Herbicides</i>	0.260	0.353	0.724	41
<i>Insecticides</i>	0.370	0.341	0.650	37
<i>Other pesticides</i>	0.303	0.307	0.588	37
<i>Variable inputs</i>	0.165	0.258	0.502	41

^aIn adherence to Murty *et al.* (2012), we also conduct additional analysis with only polluting inputs in the bad output technology. The following mean inefficiencies are reported for soil organism 0.123, water organism 0.320, fungicides 0.314, herbicides 0.350, insecticides 0.385, other pesticides 0.377 and variable inputs 0.258. The inefficiency scores show only slight differences between the two model specifications, one including non-polluting inputs (Table 2) and the other focusing solely on polluting inputs. For most indicators, inefficiency scores are marginally higher when only polluting inputs are included, suggesting that excluding non-polluting inputs may slightly increase the estimated inefficiency. The differences are particularly noticeable for insecticides and other pesticides, where inefficiency rises from 0.341 to 0.385 and from 0.307 to 0.377, respectively. However, for herbicides, the inefficiency score slightly decreases when non-polluting inputs are excluded. Despite these variations, the overall pattern remains similar, indicating that both approaches yield consistent inefficiency with minor sensitivity to input specification.

variable, where 1 indicates farms that grow potatoes and 0 indicates those that do not.

4. Results

4.1 Technical and environmental inefficiencies

Technical and environmental inefficiencies for inputs and bad outputs have been estimated relative to period-specific frontiers, in order to account for the panel structure of the data. This approach captures not only technological changes over time but also temporal variations due to weather conditions, pest incidence, crop selection and rotation patterns. Table 2 presents the mean, the second and the third quartile inefficiency scores, along with the proportion of efficient farms on the respective frontiers. Given that the distributions (Figs 1–3) are positively skewed, the quartile values offer a more representative measure of dispersion in addition to the mean. Average environmental inefficiencies are 0.317 and 0.114 for pesticide impacts on water and soil organisms, respectively. These figures indicate that, on average, farmers could reduce the environmental impact of pesticides on water and soil organisms by 31.7 and 11.4 per cent. To attain full environmental efficiency, farmers would need to reduce pesticide impacts by approximately 569 impact points per hectare for water organisms, and 44 impact points per hectare for soil organisms.

Fig. 1. The kernel density plot of environmental inefficiency for Dutch arable farms over the period 2011–21.

Among all inputs, herbicides exhibit the highest inefficiency, followed by insecticides, while other pesticides show the lowest inefficiency. The results suggest that, on average, farmers can reduce the use of fungicides by 31 per cent, herbicides by 35.3 per cent, insecticides by 34.1 per cent and other pesticides by 31 per cent. These inefficiency scores correspond to an average farm-level reduction of approximately 174 kg of fungicides, 129 kg of herbicides, 4 kg of insecticides and 157 kg of other pesticides to achieve full efficiency. Furthermore, farmers could reduce the use of all variable inputs by an average of 26 per cent. These findings imply that, under the current production technology, it is feasible to reduce both pesticide use and their environmental impacts without compromising output levels within the DEA framework.

While some farms in the sample are already operating at full efficiency and thus serve as benchmarks in the DEA model, the assumption that all farms can fully eliminate inefficiencies represents a theoretical best-case scenario intended to highlight the maximum potential for improvement in input use and environmental performance under prevailing structural and operational conditions. In practice, however, Dutch arable farms may face various structural and biophysical constraints on their production potential resulting from poor soil quality, intensive crop rotations, pest pressures and limited financial resources and management capacities.

Figures 1–3 present the kernel density distributions for environmental inefficiency and individual pesticide categories, including variable inputs. The figures indicate that the majority of farms operate close to the efficient frontier. As shown in Table 2, approximately 37–50 per cent of the observations represent best-performing peers, serving as benchmarks within their respective frontiers. With the exception of pesticide impact on soil organisms, the inefficiency scores for all pesticide categories and variable inputs exhibit distinct bi-modal distributions. This suggests that while many farms are relatively efficient, a substantial proportion also demonstrate comparatively high technical and environmental inefficiencies. The presence of bi-modal distributions may imply the influence of farm-specific contextual factors, which could be important in explaining the clustering of farms according to their pesticide use inefficiency and associated environmental impacts.

Fig. 2. The kernel density plot for pesticide inefficiency for Dutch arable farms over the period 2011–21.

Fig. 3. The kernel density plot for pesticide and variable inputs inefficiency for Dutch arable farms over the period 2011–21.

Figures 4 and 5 show the evolution of annual average environmental and pesticide inefficiencies over the period 2011–21. The variations in the inefficiencies over time offer insights into how effectively the productive capacity of inputs has been utilized within each period and how pesticide impacts have evolved.

Environmental inefficiency related to pesticide impact on water organisms is generally more volatile and consistently higher each year compared to that for soil organisms. Furthermore, there appears to be an inverse pattern in several years: when environmental inefficiency related to water organisms de-

Fig. 4. Environmental inefficiency of pesticide impacts over the period 2011–21.

Fig. 5. Technical inefficiency for different pesticide categories over the period 2011–21.

increases relative to the previous year, the inefficiency associated with soil organisms tends to increase, and vice versa. Notably, the period from 2016 to 2019 deviates from this pattern. These apparent inverse trends may be attributed to a variety of factors, including farmers’ pesticide choices, prevailing weather and environmental conditions, management priorities and the timing of pesticide application, among others.

During wetter periods, the environmental impact of pesticides on water organisms may increase due to greater runoff and leaching, while soil contamination may decline as pollutants are flushed out. Conversely, in drier conditions, limited runoff can reduce water pollution but lead to the accumulation of pesticides in the soil. Overall, although all pesticide categories exhibit year-to-year fluctuations, there is a general downward trend in inefficiency scores

Fig. 6. The kernel density plot of environmental impact points of Dutch arable farms at observed levels and with zero environmental inefficiency over the period 2011–21.

towards 2021. Among the pesticide groups, herbicides, insecticides and other pesticides display relatively moderate volatility. In contrast, fungicides exhibit greater variability, with the highest inefficiency observed in 2014 and the lowest in 2021.

Furthermore, we examined the extent to which improvements in environmental efficiency could enable farmers to meet the ALs of pesticide impacts outlined in Section 3. Figure 6 presents kernel density plots illustrating the distribution of farms based on pesticide impact points (EIP) per hectare - both in their observed state and under a hypothetical scenario where all farms operate at full environmental efficiency (i.e. with zero environmental inefficiency). For pesticide impact on soil organisms, the distribution under full environmental efficiency closely mirrors the observed distribution, with only a slight leftward shift and substantial overlap. This suggests that, for most farms, the change in EIP between the observed and fully environmentally efficient scenarios is minimal. This is consistent with the DEA results, where approximately 50 per cent of the observations exhibited no environmental inefficiency. In contrast, for pesticide impact on water organisms, the distribution under full environmental efficiency shifts noticeably to the left. This reflects the relatively higher inefficiency scores associated with water-related impacts, indicating that greater reductions in pesticide use or changes in application practices are necessary for farms to achieve full environmental efficiency in this domain.

Figure A1 a and b shows that, on average, approximately ten farms per year would meet the CTGB's acceptable threshold of 100 EIP per hectare if they operated at full environmental efficiency. Prior to achieving full environmental efficiency, only about six farms met this threshold. For pesticide impact on water organisms, no farms meet the AL in most years, except in 2011, 2013, 2019 and 2020. This implies that, although an efficiency-based approach shows potential to reduce the negative environmental impact of pesticides, its effect appears limited. This limitation suggests that improving efficiency alone may not be sufficient to meet environmental targets related to soil and water.

4.2 Determinants of inefficiency

Table 3 presents the results of the bootstrap-truncated regression models. Since the DEA computations relate to year-specific technologies, temporally fixed effects are included as dummy variables to capture the impact of time-varying factors influencing inefficiency. Additionally, the study controls for soil types and the main crop grown to avoid confounding effects and thereby improve the robustness and accuracy of the regression results. Among all individual regressions, environmental inefficiency relating to pesticide impact on water organisms had the highest number (80 per cent) of statistically significant parameters at the critical 10 per cent level or lower. It is important to note that the coefficients reflect statistical associations rather than causality. To support economic interpretation, the marginal effects of these associations are presented in Table 4. Marginal effects for ratio variables, such as specialization and debt ratio, should be interpreted carefully because a unit change represents a 100 per cent increase or decrease in the ratio variable, which can imply large changes in variable values.

Across the separate regressions, the parameter for debt ratio consistently exhibits significant and negative associations with all inefficiencies, except for environmental inefficiency related to soil organisms where the association is positive but not statistically significant. The results indicate that a unit increase in the debt ratio is associated with decreases of 4.2, 4.3, 8.0, 7.0, 8.3 and 8.7 per cent in inefficiencies related to the impact of pesticides on water organisms, fungicides, herbicides, insecticides, other pesticides and variable inputs, respectively. With respect to age, the results show that a 10-year increase in the age of the farm manager is associated with decreases of 5.2, 4.1 and 4.2 per cent in inefficiencies related to the impact of pesticides on water organisms, insecticides and variable inputs, respectively. In contrast, specialization, having insurance, cultivating potatoes and farms with predominantly clay, sandy and loess soils are all positively associated with inefficiency.

Insured farms, for example, are associated with 2.3 and 2.9 per cent increase in environmental inefficiency for pesticide impact on soil and water organisms, respectively. Moreover, they are associated with 2.7, 3.2, 5.0 and 3.8 per cent increases in the inefficiencies of herbicides, insecticides, other pesticide and variable inputs, respectively. Subsidy shows mixed associations with inefficiency. A 100 euro rise in subsidy per ha received is associated with decreases of 3.9, 4.8 and 4.1 per cent, respectively, for environmental inefficiency related to pesticide impact on soil organisms, herbicides and variable input but an increase of 6.7 per cent in environmental inefficiency related to pesticide impact on water organisms. Our results show that farms that include potatoes in their rotation are related to higher environmental inefficiency for pesticide impact on soil organisms and herbicide inefficiency. Farms on clay, sand and loess soils exhibit greater environmental inefficiency for pesticide impact on soil than those on peat soils. Similarly, clay and sand soils are linked to higher pesticide inefficiency compared to peat soils.

Table 3. Bootstrapped regression results for environmental, pesticide and variable input technical inefficiencies.

	Environmental				Pesticides			Inputs	
	Soil	Water	Fungicide	Herbicides	Insecticides	Other	Variable		
Intercept	-0.243***	0.744***	0.671***	0.549***	0.573**	0.538***	0.718***		
2012	-0.05*	-0.371***	-0.009	-0.031	-0.104***	-0.098***	-0.139***		
2013	-0.131**	-0.276***	-0.111***	0.086**	-0.101***	-0.065*	-0.096***		
2014	-0.253***	-0.159***	0.146***	-0.021	-0.023	0.020	0.095**		
2015	-0.087***	-0.159***	0.053	0.061	-0.073**	-0.067**	-0.073**		
2016	-0.067**	-0.298***	0.044	0.01	-0.103***	-0.084**	-0.085***		
2017	-0.047	-0.206***	-0.141***	0.043	-0.050	-0.039	-0.020		
2018	0.017	-0.127***	0.068	-0.022	-0.053	-0.007	-0.041		
2019	-0.080***	-0.142***	-0.126***	-0.022	-0.095***	-0.017	-0.012		
2020	-0.257***	-0.091**	-0.006	0.085*	-0.021	-0.034	-0.041		
2021	-0.052	-0.376***	-0.122**	-0.072	-0.192***	-0.215***	-0.129***		
Age	-0.020	-0.193**	-0.057	-0.036	-0.144*	-0.104	-0.146**		
Subsidy	-0.144**	0.155***	0.077	-0.154***	-0.023	-0.008	-0.133***		
Specialization	0.024	0.074	0.056	0.161**	0.100*	0.076	-0.067		
Debt ratio	0.008	-0.123**	-0.127**	-0.255***	-0.226***	-0.279***	-0.300***		
Insurance	0.040***	0.078	0.049**	0.073**	0.088**	0.131***	0.101**		
Potato farms	0.131***	0.035	-0.052	0.104*	-0.005	-0.019	0.045		
Clay	0.422***	-0.108	0.065	-0.052	-0.063	0.069*	-0.049		
Sand	0.422***	0.111***	-0.091	-0.066	0.206**	0.116***	0.001		
Loess	0.580***	-0.857	-0.110	-0.038	0.104	-0.036	-0.086		

***, ** and * indicate significance at 1, 5 and 10 per cent levels, respectively.

Table 4. Marginal effects.

	Soil	Water	Fungicide	Herbicide	Insecticide	Others	Variable
Age	0.007	-0.052**	-0.019	-0.012	-0.0e41*	-0.032	-0.042**
Subsidy	-0.039***	0.067***	0.031	-0.048**	-0.008	-0.003	-0.041***
Specialization	0.010	0.031	0.023	0.077**	0.044**	0.033	-0.021
Debt ratio	0.003	-0.042***	-0.043**	-0.080***	-0.070***	-0.085	-0.087***
Insurance	0.023***	0.29***	0.017	0.027**	0.032***	0.050***	0.038***
Potato farms	0.081***	0.013	-0.017	0.047*	-0.002	-0.006	0.022
Clay	0.397***	-0.032	-0.021	-0.017	-0.026	0.0290*	0.016
Sand	0.244***	0.044	-0.031	-0.023	0.087**	0.046***	0.000
Loess	0.222***	-0.031	-0.040	-0.014	0.038	-0.013	-0.031

***, ** and * indicate significance at 1, 5 and 10 per cent levels, respectively.

5. Discussion

The results suggest considerable potential for Dutch arable farmers to improve the efficiency of pesticide use and reduce their adverse impact on soil and water organisms. Environmental inefficiencies related to pesticide impacts represent the level of pressure exerted on the environment by farmers through their pesticide use practices, and how effectively they are mitigating such pressures. These inefficiencies can also be interpreted as an indication of the extent to which farmers protect their immediate environment. The greater potential for reducing pesticide impact on water organisms compared to soil organisms, as shown in [Table 2](#), is expected. Water ecosystems, for instance, tend to have relatively lower biodiversity, which makes them more vulnerable to the harmful effects of pesticide exposure ([Bach et al., 2020](#)). The Netherlands has relatively high levels of pesticide consumption, with a significant proportion of these compounds ending up in surface waters ([Van't et al., 2012](#)). [Didde \(2022\)](#) reports that only one per cent of Dutch water bodies are classified as being in 'good' condition, noting that it is unlikely the Netherlands will meet the requirements of the European Water Framework Directive by the 2027 deadline. The urgency to reduce the environmental impact of pesticides is underscored by the fact that agricultural productivity is closely linked to the health of flora, fauna and soil and water ecosystems ([Neemisha, 2020](#)). Therefore, there should be a strong demand for approaches and strategies that promote low- or no-pesticide practices in current and future agricultural production systems, in order to ensure a sustainable food supply.

The environmental inefficiency related to pesticide impact on soil organisms in our study is notably lower than the 24 per cent reported by [Skevas et al. \(2012\)](#) for the Netherlands during the period 2003–7. Conversely, the environmental inefficiency related to pesticide impact on water organisms is higher than the score reported by [Skevas et al. \(2012\)](#) highlighting a specific area where further improvements are needed to mitigate the adverse effects of pesticides on the environment.

Technical inefficiencies in pesticide use represent deviations from the technically optimal levels of application. These inefficiencies do not necessarily imply overuse, which is more accurately determined by assessing the Value of the Marginal Product of each pesticide. Unlike previous studies that estimate a composite inefficiency score for all pesticides combined ([Singbo et al., 2015](#)), our study demonstrates that Dutch arable farmers, on average, face distinct inefficiency gaps for individual pesticide categories. The nature of risks encountered and the timing of pesticide applications are important factors that may contribute to these differences in pesticide use inefficiency.

Herbicides exhibit the highest technical inefficiency among the pesticide categories analysed. They are the predominant method for weed control in arable crops and are applied more routinely by farmers than fungicides and insecticides ([Jørgensen et al., 2019](#)). This often pre-emptive and widespread use of herbicides is commonly adopted as a strategy to mitigate the long-term effects of weed seed shedding, which can reduce the productivity of future

crops. However, such practices may also lead to potential misuse (Finger *et al.*, 2024b).

For the majority of the farmers analysed, potato cultivation constitutes a significant portion of their overall farm production. It is typical for potato farmers to use fungicides preventively - that is, they are applied to avert potential infections (Ivanov *et al.*, 2021). Möhring *et al.* (2020d) found that 36 per cent of fungal applications among Swiss potato farmers were carried out earlier than recommended. This contrasts with the use of insecticides, which are primarily applied to reduce insect populations and thereby provide optimal growth conditions for crops. Our results could indicate that applying pesticides in anticipation of expected risks is an important factor explaining differences in inefficiencies in pesticide use. This is especially relevant when the timing of pest and disease incidences becomes more uncertain. However, the preventive use of pesticides is often linked to specific crops, suggesting that factors such as crop rotation and selection are important considerations for improving pesticide use efficiency. It is also important to recognize that pesticide use may be influenced by underlying behavioural factors, such as farmers' risk preferences and perceptions, personality traits, individual differences, biases, motivations and social norms (Finger *et al.*, 2024b). Bakker *et al.* (2021) demonstrate that Dutch farmers' intentions to reduce pesticide use are influenced by social norms. They closely observe their neighbours' practices and tend to avoid behaviours that society disapproves of.

The inefficiencies across all pesticide categories are higher compared to those of variable inputs. This may suggest that pesticide management is particularly challenging. Pesticide use efficiency can be influenced by weather and soil conditions, factors over which farmers have little or no control, and which can collectively or individually affect pest type and populations on the farm (Shahzad and Abdulai, 2020). Our reported pesticide inefficiencies align with the findings of Oude Lansink and Silva (2004) who identified a mean technical inefficiency score of 33 per cent for pesticides in the Netherlands during the period 1989–92. However, our results are higher than those reported by Skevas and Oude Lansink (2014) and Ahovi *et al.* (2021) who found pesticide inefficiencies of 25 and 24 per cent, respectively, for the Netherlands in the periods 2003–7 and 2006–16. For Catalan arable crop farms, Ait Sidhoum *et al.* (2019) reported a considerably higher pesticide inefficiency score of 63.5 per cent.

Our result for variable inputs aligns with Skevas and Oude Lansink (2014) who reported 18 per cent technical inefficiencies for variable inputs on Dutch arable farms over the period 2003–7. Over the same period, Skevas *et al.* (2012) also reported variable input technical inefficiency of approximately 18 per cent (page 557, table 5). These findings suggest that our results are consistent with established studies and highlight the persistent inefficiencies in input use observed within the sector.

Results from the second-stage bootstrap truncated regressions provide important insights into factors associated with environmental and input inefficiency. The findings show that older farmers tend to have lower inefficiency.

Age could reflect several possible explanations, such as the social cohort from which a farmer originates, experience, physical and mental capacity and the life-cycle stage of the family farm (Burton, 2014). Among these factors, experience is most frequently reported to have the strongest correlation with age (Genius *et al.*, 2006). Our results therefore suggest that, as farmers gain experience and accumulate knowledge and skills over time, they become better at optimizing pesticide use and minimizing its negative environmental impact. Zhengfei and Oude Lansink (2006) and Schneider *et al.* (2021) have also reported a similar association between age and input inefficiency among Dutch arable farmers. However, Li and Sicular (2013) and Saiyut *et al.* (2019) in their studies on the effect of age on farm performance, argue that when farmers become too old, inefficiency in input use may increase due to decreased motivation, poor health, short-term planning or unclear succession plans.

Our results suggest that the impact of subsidies varies across different inputs and environmental inefficiencies. Subsidies are associated with lower environmental inefficiencies related to pesticide impacts on soil organisms, herbicides and variable inputs, but higher inefficiencies related to pesticide impacts on water organisms. This mixed relationship between subsidies and farm efficiency has been reported in several studies (Zhu and Oude Lansink, 2010; Rizov *et al.*, 2013; Latruffe *et al.*, 2017).

There are a number of mechanisms through which subsidies can affect farm production (Bezlepkina and Oude Lansink, 2006). One important mechanism is through the income effect (Hennessy, 1998). Hennessy (1998) explains that subsidies, when invested in new technologies, can reduce inefficiency by increasing the productive capacity (efficiency) of inputs. On the other hand, farmers who may perceive subsidies as income may be less motivated to improve efficiency, relying instead on the increased income from the subsidies (Hasler *et al.*, 2022). Another explanation for the dual effects of subsidy on inefficiency could be that the subsidies recorded in the FADN originate from various sources as described in Section 3. This analysis only considered the total amount of subsidy per hectare received. Therefore, the findings suggest the need for a more nuanced examination of subsidies, analysing them in a more granular manner (Bernini and Galli, 2024).

Specialization is positively and statistically significant only with the inefficiency of herbicides and insecticides. Farmers in the sample are generally specialized, so monoculture practices are expected to be common. Such a production system, coupled with the reduced biodiversity inherent in these specialist farms, could potentially create conditions prone to pest outbreaks. With fewer natural pest control mechanisms in place, farmers may face increased pest pressure, leading to higher pesticide usage. While our result aligns with the findings of Zhu *et al.* (2023), it contrasts with Zhu and Oude Lansink (2010), who found that specialization positively contributed to overall farm technical efficiency in the Netherlands but negatively in Germany. They explain that specialized farms may capture advantages such as gaining more in-depth knowledge or benefiting from economies of scale when the scale of a single activity is relatively increased.

The results from [Zhu and Oude Lansink \(2010\)](#) also indicate that contextual factors can influence the mechanisms through which specialization can affect farm technical efficiency ([Bernini and Galli, 2024](#)). Our results imply that farmers may have over-relied on specific pesticides in the production process potentially leading to increased inefficiency.

Regarding the debt ratio, the results suggest that highly indebted farms are associated with lower environmental, pesticide and input inefficiencies. This could suggest that farms may be investing their debts in efficient innovations and technology leading to improved overall input use efficiency. However, it is important to note that farms with unsustainably high levels of debt may face challenges in accessing credit for working capital, which could hinder their ability to adopt efficiency-enhancing technologies ([Zhengfei and Oude Lansink, 2006](#)). A similar effect is observed for farms that take out weather insurance. [Möhring et al. \(2020b\)](#) found that insurance uptake is positively and economically related to pesticide use. Their study reported that, in a no-insurance scenario, pesticide use was lower by about 6–11 per cent among French and Swiss farmers. One would expect that protection from insurance should reduce incentive to use pesticide as argued by [Mishra et al. \(2005\)](#), but this relation may be mediated by the risk effect of pesticides. For example, when pesticides reduce risks, insurance can be a substitute, but when pesticides increase risk, insurance can complement them ([Möhring et al., 2020a](#)). Another plausible explanation is that insurance provides a safety net against financial losses from potential adverse weather, encouraging farmers to adopt more intensive farming practices. Confident in their financial protection, farmers may invest in better seeds, fertilizers and technology, knowing their investments are safeguarded against unforeseen weather events ([Hill and Viceisza, 2012](#)).

Our results reveal clear differences across soil types in terms of environmental inefficiency related to the pesticide impact on soil. Compared to peat soils, farms located on clay, loess and sandy soils all exhibit significantly higher inefficiencies in this dimension. These findings suggest that the physical and chemical properties of these soils influence how pesticides behave and persist in the soil environment. Clay soils, with their fine texture and strong adsorption capacity, can retain pesticides for longer periods, increasing the risk of accumulation and thus inefficiency in the soil dimension. Loess soils, which are typically silty and moderately permeable, may also allow for limited downward movement of pesticides, contributing to increased pesticide residues through partial retention near the surface. Sandy soils, by contrast, are characterized by high permeability, large pore spaces and low OM, all of which facilitate rapid infiltration and limited adsorption. [Skevas and Oude Lansink \(2014\)](#) also report similar relationships between farming on sandy soils and environmental and pesticide inefficiencies for Dutch arable farms over the period 2003–7.

While this study provides valuable insights, it is important to acknowledge its limitations. One limitation is the lack of data on the qualitative properties of the pesticides used, which are important criteria for farmers' application

decisions (Möhring *et al.*, 2020a). This study expressed pesticide usage in kilograms of active ingredient per farm; however, the toxicity of active ingredients per kilogram may have changed over time. Future research could incorporate the qualitative properties of pesticides at the product level and develop an indicator that captures the balance between volume and toxicity, thereby improving performance evaluation and comparison. Furthermore, our analysis only considered the financial, technical and socio-economic factors provided in the data, meaning that other relevant technologies not reported could not be incorporated.

6. Conclusion and policy implications

This paper employed the by-production specification proposed by Murty *et al.* (2012) and Dakpo (2016) to measure inefficiency in the use of pesticides and the generation of undesirable outputs alongside intended (good) outputs. Next, we used a bootstrap truncated regression to explore the factors underlying differences in inefficiency scores across farms. The empirical application focused on panel data from Dutch arable farms over the period 2011–21.

We conclude from the estimated inefficiencies of pesticide use and associated bad outputs (i.e. pesticide pollution) that there is considerable potential for farmers to improve pesticide use efficiency and reduce their environmental impacts on soil and water organisms. The potential for improving pesticide efficiency is highest for herbicides (35.3 per cent), followed by insecticides (34.1 per cent), fungicides (31.1 per cent) and other pesticides (30.7 per cent). The results indicate a significantly greater potential to reduce the impact of pesticides on water organisms (31.7 per cent) compared to soil organisms (10.8 per cent). This suggests that reductions in pesticide impacts on water organisms are more readily achievable, as there is a larger margin for improvement while still maintaining output value. However, even with full environmental efficiency, majority of farmers would not meet acceptable pesticide impact levels.

Results from the second-stage regression indicate that farm-specific contextual factors may have important implications for improving the efficiency of pesticide use. Older farmers, given their experience, could play a key role in enhancing pesticide use efficiency and reducing their adverse environmental effects. The impact of subsidies on inefficiency is mixed: while they are associated with lower environmental inefficiency related to pesticide impact on soil organisms and with variable input inefficiency, they are linked to increased inefficiency related to pesticide impact on water organisms, suggesting potential misallocation. Specialization in farming is associated with higher inefficiency in herbicide and insecticide use, implying that specialized farmers might over-rely on specific pesticides or manage them less efficiently. Additionally, a higher debt ratio is consistently linked to lower environmental and pesticide inefficiencies, whereas farms that take insurance exhibit higher inefficiencies, suggesting that risk mitigation may lead to less careful resource use.

Lastly, farms that include potatoes in their crop rotation and those operating on sandy soils are associated with higher inefficiency.

Our results have several other policy implications. The current production technology is limited in enabling the vast majority of farmers to reduce pesticide use to ALs of environmental impact. Therefore, while improving technical efficiency remains important, our findings indicate that efficiency gains alone are insufficient to achieve pesticide environmental impact targets. Consequently, efficiency improvements need to operate in tandem with systemic agronomic and pest management changes. IPM can offer such a complementary pathway by aligning pest control decisions more closely with actual pest pressures and crop conditions (Barzman *et al.*, 2015). Through regular pest monitoring, threshold-based spraying and the use of forecasting tools, IPM prevents unnecessary or mistimed applications, ensuring pesticides are used only when economically and ecologically justified. Complementary practices such as biological control, crop diversification and the use of resistant varieties further lower baseline pest pressure, thereby increasing the marginal productivity of each unit of pesticide applied. Moreover, selective pesticide choice, rotation of active ingredients and precision application technologies help maintain long-term effectiveness and reduce input waste. Together, these measures enhance both technical and environmental efficiency by minimizing redundant pesticide use while sustaining yields, thereby moving farms closer to the attainable efficiency frontier under real-world biophysical and management constraints.

Importantly, our results also indicate that farms with higher debt-to-asset ratios tend to exhibit lower inefficiency levels. In the Dutch context - where agriculture is highly capital-intensive and technologically advanced - this association may reflect the role of financial leverage in driving managerial discipline, innovation adoption and responsiveness to market and regulatory pressures. Farms carrying higher levels of debt are likely to be more professionally managed and better equipped to implement efficiency-enhancing technologies and practices, including IPM (Zhengfei and Oude Lansink, 2006). Based on this finding, policymakers and financial institutions could consider how access to appropriate financing structures might support further improvements in farm efficiency and sustainability while ensuring financial risks remain manageable.

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Appendix 1

Figure A1 a and b shows the potential impact of improving environmental efficiency on the number of farms that meet the acceptable authorization level as described in Section 3.1. The technically optimal levels of pesticide impact on both soil and water organisms per hectare for each farm in each year are compared to the respective ALs. The comparison is used to determine the number of farms that have their technically optimal levels of pesticide impact below the acceptable threshold.

Fig. A1. Number of farms achieving the acceptable level of pesticide impact on soil and water organisms.

Appendix 2

The following properties apply to the good output technology $\psi_g(t)$:

- g1. No free lunch and inactivity.
- g2. Input essentiality and attainability.
- g3. Non-emptiness and closeness.
- g4. Boundedness.
- g5. Positive monotonicity in (t) : if $v(t) \in \psi_g(t)$ and $v'(t) \geq v(t)$, then $v'(t) \in \psi_g(t)$.
- g6. Positive monotonicity in (t) : if $p(t) \in \psi_g(t)$ and $p'(t) \geq p(t)$, then $p'(t) \in \psi_g(t)$.
- g7. Free disposability of good outputs: $y(t) \in \psi_g(t)$ and $y'(t) \leq y(t)$, then $y'(t) \in \psi_g(t)$.
- g8. Reverse nestedness in $f(t)$: if $k(t) \in \psi_g(t)$ and $k'(t) \geq k(t)$, then $k'(t) \in \psi_g(t)$. Similarly, if $f(t) \in \psi_g(t)$ and $f'(t) \geq f(t)$, then $f'(t) \in \psi_g(t)$.
- g9. Convexity in $v(t), p(t), f(t)$ and $y(t)$.

Properties of the bad output technology $\psi_b(t)$ are in contrast to the good output technology $\psi_g(t)$.

- b1. Polluting inputs essentiality $(v(t), p(t))$.
- b2. Boundedness.
- b3. Negative monotonicity $v(t)$: if $v(t) \in \psi_b(t)$ and $v'(t) \leq v(t)$, then $v'(t) \in \psi_b(t)$.
- b4. Negative monotonicity $p(t)$: if $p(t) \in \psi_b(t)$ and $p'(t) \leq p(t)$, then $p'(t) \in \psi_b(t)$.
- b5. Positive monotonicity $b(t)$: if $b(t) \in \psi_b(t)$ and $b'(t) \geq b(t)$, then $b'(t) \in \psi_b(t)$.
- b6. Convexity in $v(t), p(t), f(t)$ and $b(t)$.

Appendix 3

$$y_o(t) \leq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n y_n^g(t)$$

$$v_o(t) - \beta_v g_v \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n v_n^g(t)$$

$$fu(t) - \beta_{fu} g_{fu} \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n fu_n^g(t)$$

$$he_o(t) - \beta_{he} g_{he} \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n he_n^g(t)$$

$$in_o(t) - \beta_{in} g_{in} \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n in_n^g(t)$$

$$os_o(t) - \beta_{os} g_{os} \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n os_n^g(t)$$

$$f_o(t) \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n f_n^g(t)$$

$$b_o(t) - \beta_b g_b \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n y_n^b(t)$$

$$v_o(t) - \beta_v g_v \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n v_n^b(t)$$

$$fu_o(t) - \beta_{fu} g_{fu} \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n fu_n^b(t)$$

$$he_o(t) - \beta_{he} g_{he} \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n he_n^b(t)$$

$$in_o(t) - \beta_{in} g_{in} \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n in_n^b(t)$$

$$os_o(t) - \beta_{os} g_{os} \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n os_n^b(t)$$

$$f_o(t) \geq \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n f_n^b(t)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n v_n^b(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n v_n^g(t), \quad \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n fu_n^b(t) = \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n fu_n^g(t)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n h e_n^b(t) &= \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n h e_n^g(t), & \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n i n_n^b(t) &= \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n h e_n^g(t) \\ & \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n o s_n^b(t) &= \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n o s_n^g(t), \\ \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n f_n^b(t) &= \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n f_n^g(t), & \sum_{n=1}^N \lambda_n &= 1, & \sum_{n=1}^N \varphi_n &= 1. \end{aligned}$$